

DRAFT PERFORMANCE STANDARD FOR COLOR AMLCDs IN U.S. MILITARY AIRCRAFT: Recommended Best Practice

Darrel G. Hopper

Wright Laboratory (AFMC), Cockpit Avionics Office

WL/AAA-2 Bldg 146, 2210 Eighth St Ste 1, Wright Patterson AFB OH 45433-7511 USA

Phone: (513) 255-8261, Fax: (513) 476-4547, E-mail: hopperdg@wl.wpafb.af.mil

ABSTRACT

There are no standards, commercial or military, for active matrix liquid crystal displays (AMLCDs). One is being developed to provide guidance to procurement programs for U.S. military airborne cockpit applications. Other applications will have less severe requirements which would affect backlight and design, including mission and cabin displays. A draft standard comprising recommended best practices has been published. It is useful to procurement programs in drafting their performance specification, to integrators in determining if a commercial specification can meet that performance specification, and to industry in the establishment of common AMLCDs in military aircraft and common AMLCD design elements wherever possible across all civil and military avionic applications.

INTRODUCTION

A new epoch in flight instrument technology has arrived. Electromechanical (EM), cathode ray tube (CRT) displays are being superseded by flat panel active matrix liquid crystal displays (AMLCDs) in all classes of flight instrument: military, commercial, general, and space. A similar transition has begun too in other applications having similar requirements, such as maintenance notebook computers, field laptop communication suitcases, and land vehicle driver's viewing systems. This transformation will accelerate during the mid-1990s. AMLCDs have significantly increased the display capability realizable in fielded applications in several key regards, including performance, life-cycle costs, display size, weight, and power. It is no longer necessary, for example, to accept displays that are not full color, can not be read in full sunlight, are not affordable.

The Cockpit Avionics Office initiated the a functional performance specification for FPCDs and a standard for AMLCDs for militarized flight instruments in April 1992. The first phase was reported here last year [1]. The

second phase completed in Jun 94 with the publication of the draft standard [2]. The third phase will involve finalization of this draft standard for color AMLCDs in combat system applications and initiation of a technology independent performance standard for flat panel displays in military cockpits and other combat human system interfaces [3]. All concerned parties are welcome to participate in this process.

No such common specification or standard exists and it is absolutely necessary that they be developed prior to the impending revolution in fielded electronic displays. Furthermore, the standard may permit us to capitalize on the opportunity to establish common display modules for use in several platforms across services. The specification and standard are to be as common as practicable with other military and commercial uses, such as the work on display standards for commercial flight decks by Lamberth and Penn [4]. Commercial standards in non-avionic applications are planned but nothing has been begun; thus the present effort for military aircraft is a dual use activity.

AMLCD technology is the first of a new generation. Thus, the first standard is specifically for AMLCD display head modules. A general, or guide, specification for electronically and optically generated airborne displays, independent of any particular technology, has recently been published [5]. Standards for other flat panel display technologies will be prepared separately as needed; many such technologies are in R&D [6].

PERFORMANCE BASELINE AND GOALS

Standards are now being developed for AMLCD digital flight instruments. Sizes worthy of consideration for a DOD standard product list include those listed in Table I. The consumer electronics mass market customer will not pay for many features or sizes that are absolutely necessary to the military customer. Hence, features vital to military aircraft flight instruments and other military applications, such as a front-line field notebook

computer, will not be found in AMLCDs coming off of any high volume commercial line. Similarly for most of the sizes. Its purely a matter of business. Thus, the government must bear the cost of some militarized production since it is the most demanding customer. On the other hand, the most demanding applications typically force the creation of solutions in the form of new technologies which in turn create new industries and jobs. Needed performance metrics are presented as goals wherever they cannot be met by 1994 manufacturing technology.

The design baseline for flight instruments comprises a-Si TFT (or CdSe TFT) on glass substrate with chip-on-flex 16-graylevel drivers and a backlight system using fluorescent tubes coupled with dimming circuitry (685 nt upper limit for day, down to a lower limit of 0.10 nt for night) and 10:1 contrast. The preferred pixel shape is square (RGBG quad-square subpixel elements for color) with addressable element density of about 6.3 mm^{-1} (160 in^{-1}) in direct view and 38.8 mm^{-1} (985 in^{-1}) in helmet/head mounted. The design goal is *at least* one pixel every 100 arcseconds (485 mrad) across the field-of-view.

As AMLCD technology is at the very beginning of its use in operational applications, rapid improvements in design options are anticipated. Variations and improvements on the baseline may be made when both device R&D and manufacturing technology are completed. Other semiconductor materials under development include p-Si and x-Si. Drivers may be upgraded to chip-on-glass technology or integrated on the periphery of the display substrate. Drivers will be upgraded to 64, 128, and 256 graylevels. Backlight systems will be re-invented in a variety of innovative ways to provide ten times the lumens/watt presently available in a production unit. Dimming circuitry will become 40000:1 to handle the full luminance range of 1400 to 0.03 nt at 50:1 contrast ratio. Horizontal pixel densities need to be doubled in direct view displays to accommodate autostereoscopic 3D without losing resolution. Pixel shape and greyscale may become less important as resolution increases. The goal for pixel resolution is *at most* one every 50 arcseconds (250 mrad).

The sunlight readability performance requirements break into two broad classes: sun in the eye and sun on the display. AMLCD is the first technology to truly meet the users need for sunlight legibility in both cases. Several systems, commercial civil and military (C-17, F/A-18C/D, F-15, A-10) have had problems with dichroic LCDs. The pilots cannot read dichroics in either sunlight readability extreme. The literature on dichroic LCDs

recommends against the use dichroic LCDs in bright ambient applications, and has for a decade or so. Yet display integrators continue to foist DLCDs on systems integrators. The final integrator is the pilot. A typical pilot comment regarding DLCDs is "remove them and leave an empty place in the instrument panel for my gloves so I can get some use out of the space". The same comment applied to CRTs in many situations, with the additional problem of low MTBF in CRTs. AMLCDs do not have the problems associated with dichroic LCDs or with CRTs, and yet are readable in full sunlight.

Several companies have improved the backlight scheme so as to achieve sufficient backlight intensity. See the eight papers in the backlight section of the *Cockpit Displays* conference.[7] The issue now is how much is too much. The excess capability of the technology can be taken in a reduction in the power required, which in turn reduces the heat dissipation problem (such as C-130 RAMTIP, C-141, and other transports) and helps with power generation constraints (such as F-15E).

Studies are underway to obtain data for the upper limit luminance required in the situation where the ambient illumination is a sun lamp shining directly into the eyes of the test-subjects [8]. The results are pertinent to the situation of the sun shining in the operator's eyes, such as a pilot flying toward a sunset or a field commander riding into a sunrise. Preliminary results indicated that the goal for the high end is 1200-1370 nt (350-400 fL).

Dual use applications are emerging with environmental operational requirements similar to military cockpits. Ruggedized applications such as automotive and fire fighting are finding that their requirements should be more ruggedized than they previously had thought.

COMMON SIZES

Table I summarizes all the data which could be obtained by Jun 94 on the AMLCDs which have been built, are being designed or proposed for current and future platforms, such as the F-22, F-18, and C-141. Updates to Table I are requested.

One need not look beyond sizes and pixel definitions to realize the need and the potential for standard products. These candidates are representative of the variety of AMLCD flight instruments developed, or in development, since 1988. None of these is a standard item in any aircraft system; but some of them soon will be. Thus, engineers working different aircraft programs throughout DOD need to come together rapidly while

TABLE I. Current AMLCD Display Module Size and Characteristics

Table I summarizes all the data which could be obtained by Jun 94 on the AMLCDs which have been built, are being designed or proposed for current and future platforms, such as the F-22, F-18, and C-141. This table specifies, where available, size, viewing angle, gray shades, luminance, and whether it displays monochrome or color information for each AMLCD. Display size is the active image area. The convention adopted here for all dimensions (angles, pixels, distance) is to give horizontal (width) first followed by vertical (height). Viewing angle is relative to normal at center point of display, with the convention that left and down are negative. Unless stated otherwise: pixels are square; mono pixels are not subdivided into subpixels; and color pixels are subdivided into four square subpixels (RGBG). All displays have active matrix implemented in the form of thin-film transistors (TFT), rather than metal-insulator-metal (MIM) diodes. All displays are fabricated in amorphous silicon (a-Si), except RAH-66, EH-101, C-130J displays, which are cadmium selenide (CdSe). One need not look beyond sizes and pixel definitions to realize the need and the potential for standard products. These candidates are representative of the variety of AMLCD flight instruments developed, or in development, since 1988. None of these is a standard item in any aircraft system; but some of them soon will be. Thus, engineers working different aircraft programs throughout DOD need to come together rapidly while the opportunity for common, standard sizes is still wide open. As the products listed in Table I mature, other procurement programs may elect to use them rather than develop additional designs of their own. The very summary in one place of all the sizes and types may help the integrators converge on a necessary and sufficient set. Updates to this Table are requested.

Display Size mm (in.) <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Platform	Resolution pixels <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Viewing Angle degrees <i>left, right down, up</i>	Gray Levels	Color/ Mono	Minimum Luminance nt (fL)
343 x 224 (13.5 x 8.8)	Lamps II	1280 x 1024			color	
292 x 218 (11.5 x 8.6)	Air Force 1					
275 x 206 (10.82 x 8.12)	EH-101	768 x 576			color	
261 x 261 (10.3 x 10.3)	experimental	1024 x 1024			color	
211 x 158 (8.31 x 6.24)	terminal	640 x 480	-45, +45 -30, +10	256	color	0 - 172 (0 -50)
211 x 157 (8.3 x 6.2)	portable workstation	640 x 480 and 1024 x 768		64	color	

TABLE I. Current AMLCD Display Module Sizes and Characteristics (continued)

Display Size mm (in.) <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Platform	Resolution pixels <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Viewing Angle degrees <i>left, right down, up</i>	Gray Levels	Color/ Mono	Minimum Luminance nt (fL)
203 x 152 (8.0 x 6.0) Map Figures Charts	RAH-66* B-52 B-1 V-22 E-2C AH-64 Flightline Maintenance Field Comm. Suitcase	640 x 480		256	color SQ-4vs	634 (185)
203 x 152 (8.0 x 6.0) FLIR/ LLTV	RAH-66* UH-1N SH-60 B-52 B-1 V-22 EH-101 Army trucks	1280 x 480	-28.2, +7.7 -10.5,+12.7	256	mono VS-1vs	634 (185)
198 x 198 (7.8 x 7.8)	F-22* EF-111	640 x 640	-25, +25 -0, +15	16	color	0.3 - 685 (0.1 - 200)
198 x 158 (7.81 x 6.23)	SH-60 LAMPS II	640 x 512			color	
196 x 145 (7.7 x 5.7)	P-3C U-IV	640 x 400	-60, +60 -20, +20	2	mono	0.34 - 856 (0.1 - 250)
196 x 146 (7.66 x 5.74)	EH-101	768 x 576	-50, +50 -20, +20	16	color	0.17 - 445 (0.05-130)
170 x 170 (6.71 x 6.71)	Space Shuttle* EC-3A	1152 x 960 video mode 770 x 576 graphics	-60, +60 -10, +45	56	color	0.17 - 343 (0.05-100)
170 x 170 (6.7 x 6.7)	B-777	1152 x 1152 graphics + video bus	-55, +55 -5, +30	56	color DL-3sq	0.17 - 343 (0.05-100)

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Display Size mm (in.) <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Platform	Resolution pixels <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Viewing Angle degrees <i>left, right down, up</i>	Gray Levels	Color/ Mono	Minimum Luminance nt (fL)
159 x 159 (6.25 x 6.25)	YF-22 F-22* F-18 E/F Tiger Rafaele	512 x 512	-25, +25 -0, +15	16	color	0.3 - 685 (0.1 - 200)
159 x 159 (6.25 x 6.25)	F/A-18E/F	512 x 512	-15, +15 -5, +35	32	color	0.17 - 685 (0.05-200)
155 x 206 (6.1 x 8.1)	C-141* C-130 P-3 B-727 C-5 KC-135 KC-10	480 x 640 and 512 x 640	-60, +60 -5, +35	8 to 64 and 525 raster	color	0.3 - 685 (0.1 -200)
152 x 203 (6.0 x 8.0)	C-130 RAMTIP C-130J	480 x 640		32	color	548 (160)
152 x 152 (6.0 x 6.0)	YF-23* Tank F-16 FMS T-38	480 x 480		64	color	
152 x 76 (6.0 x 3.0)	C-130				color	
127 x 127 (5 x 5)	F-4, F-5 T-45 Migs, Kfir helicopters				color	
127 x 102 (5 x 4)	YF-22				mono	
126 x 99.1 (4.95 x 3.9)	F/A-18E/F* EF-111	767 x 605	-15, +15 -10, +40	32	mono	685 (200)
121 x 121 (4.75 x 4.75)	F-5	875 x 525		video, 10	mono	0.34 - 856 (0.1 -250)
121 x 25 (4.75 x 1.0)	F-117A				mono	

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Display Size mm (in.) <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Platform	Resolution pixels <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Viewing Angle degrees <i>left, right down, up</i>	Gray Levels	Color/ Mono	Minimum Luminance nt (fL)
114 x 99 (4.5 x 3.5) HSI/ADI/radio	C-130H	410 x 328	-45, +45 -10, +30**	16	color DL-3vs	
114 x 88.9 (4.5 x 3.5)	F/A-18E/F			32	mono	
114 x 88.9 (4.5 x 3.5)	CL-415				color DL-3vs	206 (60)
102 x 152 (4.0 x 6.0)	YF-22				mono	
102 x 102 (4.0 x 4.0)	F-16C/D* C-130A	482 x 482	-25, +25 -10, +30	32 and 64	color DL-3sq	617 (180)
99.1 x 99.1 (3.9 x 3.9)	F-15	512 x 512		525 raster +graphics	color	
99 x 99 (3.9 x 3.9)	CH-46E	640 480			color	
99.1 x 73.7 (3.9 x 2.9)	F-22	320 x 240	-25, +25 -0, +15	bi-level dot matrix	color	685 (200)
90 x 170 (3.5 x 6.7)	RAH-66	288 x 544			mono	
86.4 x 73.7 (3.4 x 2.9)	Tiger					
86.1 x 73.4 (3.39 x 2.89)	F-15E* SH-60 KC-135 EC-3A	414 x 468			color DL-3sq	
76.7 x 57.7 (3.02 x 2.27)	C-130J	480 x 360			mono	
75 x 75 (3.0 3.0)	4ATI	480 x 480	-45, +45 0, +35	16	color RGWB	0.3 - 343 (0.1 - 100)
63.5 x 88.9? (2.5 x 3.5?)	C-141				mono	548 (160)

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Display Size mm (in.) <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Platform	Resolution pixels <i>horiz. x vert.</i>	Viewing Angle degrees <i>left, right down, up</i>	Gray Levels	Color/ Mono	Minimum Luminance nt (fL)
57.6 x 57.6 (2.27 x 2.27)	3ATI	480 x 480	-45, +45 0, +35	16	color RGWB	0.3 - 343 (0.1 - 100)
50.8 x 50.8 (2.0 x 2.0)	C-130H	164 x 164	±60		color	
50 x 25 (2 x 1) ?	F-15 FMS				mono	

* Data gathered for this aircraft; data for other systems in this row may differ.

** Center of viewing cone can be steered electronically ±10° vertically ,
from (-20, + 20) to (0, + 40).

? Incomplete data on size.

the opportunity for common, standard sizes is still wide open. As the products listed in Table I mature, other procurement programs may elect to use them rather than develop additional designs of their own. The very summary in one place of all the sizes and types may help the integrators converge on a necessary and sufficient set.

of developing these requirement, specification, and standard documents can request inclusion from the author. This process is will lead to documents beneficial to both government and industry.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a need for a common performance specification for FPCDs and a standard for AMLCDs for military applications, beginning with cockpit flight instruments. Such documents provide guidance in the preparation of product performance specifications by a product center, logistic center, depot, or vendor. The specification and standard cut across all systems and applications. Privity often prevents the end customer, i.e. the U.S. Government, from interfering in the relationship between a display manufacturer and a flight instrument integrator in a contractual food chain. This FPCD performance specification and AMLCD standard will provide government guidance to all such relationships. There is also the possibility of a common military products. Institutions that have not thus far been part of the process

6. REFERENCES

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